

Background

Finland

- As part of the REPowerEU plan, the aims of EU Solar Strategy is to double solar
- City of Helsinki is following EU regulations
- The city has been installing PV panels on **new service buildings** (mostly educational or healthcare) they owned and also on some **existing buildings**.

**** Finland's National Energy and Climate Strategy will be completed and updated in spring 2025.**

Electricity generation development in Finland

Projected development of electricity generation (TWh)

FINGRID

Fingrid estimate, September 2024

Projected development of solar power.

Solar power

Fingrid estimate, September 2024

FINGRID

Land occupation of roof top/ground-mounted PV

1 point is equivalent to the impacts (in species-year) of 1 person (globally) over 1 year

Key take aways

- Finland has plan to significantly increase solar energy.
- Depending on **PV technology** GHG emissions can be lower or higher than other **renewables** (compared to hydro, wind; **Silicon-based PV** has higher GHG; **CdTe** and **CIGS** has lower GHG)
- **Roof-mounted PV** has significantly lower ecosystem impact than **ground-mounted PV**.

Pre-workshop Questions

Building-Integrated Photovoltaics

Definitions

- **BIPV (Building-Integrated Photovoltaics)** Panels are designed to replace conventional building materials such as roofing, facades, or windows. They generate solar power while also serving as a functional part of the building's structure.

Type of PV

Crystalline silicon solar cells

- Market share 95%
- Economically viable
- 25 – 30 years lifetime

Thin-film solar cells

- Market share 5%
- Used under special circumstance (weight restriction)
 - 10 – 20 years lifetime

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

2. Flexible solar panels are more than just off-grid staples). Retrieved 15 April 2025, from <https://www.solarpowerworldonline.com/2021/05/flexible-solar-panels-are-more-than-just-off-grid-staples/>

3. Solar PV Panel Types That Are High In Demand. Retrieved 15 April 2025, from <https://intersolarsystems.com/solar-pv-panel-types-that-are-high-in-demand/>

Interconnection Technologies for PV

Standard busbar interconnection

Wire interconnection

Metal wrap-through interconnection

Half-cell busbar interconnection

Interdigitated back contact interconnection

Shingled interconnection

Fixing solutions for façade PV

linear frame
screwed on site

continuous
clamping

individual/point
clamping

point fixing with
drilled holes

Adhesive vertical
rail with hooks

Adhesive self-weight
system with safety
mechanical retention

continuous post-
and-rail façade
system

Bifacial and Monofacial PV

Bifacial PV

Monofacial PV

Vertical Bifacial PV

1. BiFacial Photovoltaic, Knowledge center - international solar training academyh. Retrieved 29 April 2025, from <https://istindia.org/support/know-BiFacial-Photovoltaic.php>
2. Badran, G., Dhimish, M. Comprehensive study on the efficiency of vertical bifacial photovoltaic systems: a UK case study. *Sci Rep* **14**, 18380 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-68018-1>
3. Bellini, E. (2022, April 26). Japan's first vertical agrivoltaic project. *pv magazine International*. <https://www.pv-magazine.com/2022/04/26/japans-first-vertical-agrivoltaic-project/>

Vertical Bifacial PV and Load matching

1. V. Bergpob, S. Jouttijärvi, M. Jänkäälä, and K. Miettunen, "Performance of vertically mounted bifacial photovoltaics under the physical influence of low-rise residential environment in high-latitude locations," *Frontiers in Built Environment*, vol. 10, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/built-environment/articles/10.3389/fbuil.2024.1343036>. [Accessed: Apr. 01, 2025].

Different building integration solutions for Bifacial PV

Novel Solar Panel?

1. FuturaSun's latest range of coloured photovoltaic modules. Retrieved 07 August 2025 from <https://www.futurasun.com/en/silk-nova-silver-96-cells/>
2. Solar design collections from Solarix. Retrieved 07 August 2025 from <https://solarix-solar.com/en/collection>
3. Novel Panel from Ertex Brochure. Retrieved 07 August 2025 from <https://www.ertex-solar.at/en/downloads/brochures/>

PV maintenance

1. Facade cleaning with robot _ hyCLEANER. Retrieved 13 May 2025, from <https://hycleaner.de/en/facade-cleaning/>
2. Solar Panel Installation Retrieved 13 May 2025, from <https://energyefficiency.ie/solar-panels/installation/>

Reasons to consider Façade BIPV

- Due to low sun angle, BIPV façades is suitable in regions with latitudes of 45 degrees or higher (Nordic countries)/
- Integrate PV into façade system can be cost competitive compared to conventional façade system (due to energy saving from PV).
- Scaling up PV system to match electricity consumption can be implemented easier on façade than on roof (especially in the case of tall buildings).

Case Studies

Umwelt Arena, Spreitenbach, Switzerland, 2012

Roof BIPV application

Opaque m-Si PV technology

101.3 kWh/m² Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

540 MWh Annual electricity generation

Umwelt Arena, Spreitenbach, Switzerland, 2012

Net floor area = 12,700 m²

BIPV roof area = 5,333 m²

Folzano kindergarten, Folzano, Italy, 2010

Roof BIPV application

Opaque amorphous-Si PV technology

77 kWh/m²

Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

13 MWh Annual electricity generation

Folzano kindergarten, Folzano, Italy, 2010

Panel info:

Flexible a-Si thin-film modules use aluminium as a backsheet and are 2.849 m × 0.537 m and weigh 9.2 kg

BIPV roof area = 168 m²

Glasberga residential district, Södertälje, Sweden, 2020

Roof BIPV application

CdTe solar shingles PV technology

73.5 kWh/m² Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

104.4 MWh Annual electricity generation

Glasberga residential district, Södertälje, Sweden, 2020

Figure 5.29 Glasberga. Plan view drawing. Credits: adapted by Ana Marco Castro from Soltech Energy Sweden®, Credits: Soltech Energy Sweden.

1. BIPV roofing

1

Not to scale

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Azurmendi Restaurant, Bilbao Madrid, Spain, 2015

Skylight and curtain wall BIPV application

Semi-transparent amorphous Si PV technology

66 kWh/m² Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

16.4 MWh Annual electricity generation

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>
2. Azurmendi restaurant _ Eurac Research. Retrieved 29 April 2025, from <https://integratedpv.eurac.edu/en/case-studies/azurmendi-restaurant.html>

Azurmendi Restaurant, Bilbao Madrid, Spain, 2015

Edmonton Convention Centre, Edmonton, Canada, 2020

Skylight BIPV application

Semi-transparent m-Si PV technology

128 kWh/m² Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

Retrofit Construction

200 MWh Annual electricity generation

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Edmonton Convention Centre, Edmonton, Canada, 2020

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Gothenburg garage, Gothenburg, Sweden, 2021

Solar Shading BIPV application

Semi-transparent coloured CdTe PV technology

21 kWh/m²
Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

16.9 MWh
Annual electricity generation

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Gothenburg garage, Gothenburg, Sweden, 2021

Not to scale

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Solaris 416, Zurich, Switzerland, 2017

Roof and rainscreen BIPV application

Opaque colored m-Si PV technology

53 kWh/m²

Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

31.8 MWh Annual electricity generation

Solaris 416, Zurich, Switzerland, 2017

1300 BIPV modules from Ertex Solar that cover 400 m² of the southern and western façades and 200 m² of the roof

Brown cladding made of ribbed cast glass that hides the PV cells

DeltaROSSO, Vacallo, Switzerland, 2016

Roof and Rainscreen BIPV application

Opaque m-Si
PV technology

161 kWh/m² Annual electricity generation
per BIPV module area

New Construction

48.9 MWh Annual electricity generation

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

DeltaROSSO, Vacallo, Switzerland, 2016

The roof includes 109 m² of BIPV tiles with a peak power of 17 kW, while the surface area on the BIPV façade is 194 m² of BIPV modules with a peak power of 30 kW.

Manitou a bi Bii Daziigae, Red River College Polytechnic, Winnipeg, Manitoba, 2022

Rainscreen BIPV application

Opaque coloured m-Si (BIPV), Bifacial m-Si (rooftop) PV technology

112 kWh/m² Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

80 MWh (BIPV) + 89 MWh (rooftop) Annual electricity generation

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Manitou a bi Bii Daziigae, Red River College Polytechnic,
Winnipeg, Manitoba, 2022

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>
2. Hewitt, C. (2021, September 21). *Manitou a bi Bii daziigae*. SMS Engineering. Retrieved April 29, 2025, from <https://www.smseng.com/post/manitou-bi-bii-daziigae>

Urban park in Certosa Island, Venice, Italy, 2020

Roof BIPV application

Opaque colored Si PV technology

192 kWh/m² Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

Retrofit Construction, **UNESCO heritage site**

211 MWh Annual electricity generation

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>
2. La Certosa Island _ Eurac Research. Retrieved 29 April 2025, from <https://integratedpv.eurac.edu/en/case-studies/la-certosa-island.html>

Urban park in Certosa Island, Venice, Italy, 2020

Tilt angle of 18° to 25°, the glass-glass-coloured modules have been used

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>
2. La Certosa Island _ Eurac Research. Retrieved 29 April 2025, from <https://integratedpv.eurac.edu/en/case-studies/la-certosa-island.html>

Franklin University Student Residence, Sorengo, Switzerland, 2023

Solar Shading BIPV application

Colored Opaque mc-Si PV technology

102 kWh/m²
Annual electricity generation per BIPV module area

New Construction

18.7 MWh
Annual electricity generation

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Franklin University Student Residence, Sorengo, Switzerland, 2023

Dynamic system of white photovoltaic louvres and it features one of Europe's first vertical photovoltaic louvres that follow the sun's orientation.

1. Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>
2. New campus Franklin University Switzerland. Solarchitecture. <https://solarchitecture.ch/new-campus-franklin-university-switzerland/>

Other Case Studies

UNStudio Completes Remodeling Works of the Hanwha HQ in Seoul. (2020). Retrieved 8 April 2022, from <https://www.archdaily.com/938302/unstudio-completes-remodeling-works-of-the-hanwha-hq-in-seoul>

Green Dot Animo Leadership High School / Brooks + Scarpa Architects. (2013). Retrieved 24 May 2023, from <https://www.archdaily.com/340616/green-dot-animo-leadership-high-school-brooks-scarpa-architects>

Training Academy Mont-Cenis Herne - sbp. (2023). Retrieved 24 May 2023, from <https://www.sbp.de/en/project/training-academy-mont-cenis-herne/>

Porta Susa AV Station, Turin, Italy, 2013 from Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

Nursery +E In Marburg / Opus Architekten. (2015). Retrieved 21 April 2022, from <https://www.archdaily.com/641051/nursery-e-in-marburg-opus-architekten>

Nursery +E In Marburg / Opus Architekten. (2015). Retrieved 21 April 2022, from <https://www.archdaily.com/641051/nursery-e-in-marburg-opus-architekten>

Copenhagen International School Nordhavn / C.F. Møller. (2017). Retrieved 24 May 2023, from <https://www.archdaily.com/879152/copenhagen-international-school-nordhavn-cf-moller>

Fanshawe College Innovation Village, London, Ontario, 2023 from Martín Chivelet, N., Kapsis, C., & Frontini, F. (2025). Building-Integrated Photovoltaics: A Technical Guidebook doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003432241>

How Danish Architects Connect with Users to Provide Them With the Best Architecture Possible. (2016). Retrieved 8 April 2022, from https://www.archdaily.com/774376/how-danish-architects-connect-with-users-to-provide-them-with-the-best-architecture-possible?ad_medium=gallery

Freiburg Town Hall / ingenhoven architects. (2017). Retrieved 8 April 2022, from <https://www.archdaily.com/885885/freiburg-town-hall-ingenhoven-architects>

Design Task

Design Brief and Task (45 mins)

You have been asked by your client to meet their building's energy demands for the building that you are designing now. The client is quite important, as they all are, and they have requested a meeting at the end of the day to see some possible design options for their building integrated with solar energy generation.

Today, you have received a list of solar panels from your consultant (next page). The list contains information on the typical size of panels and annual energy yield in kWh/kWp for different orientations of the panels (Schram & Shirazi, 2025).

Now, you have 45 minutes to prepare a design option for your client. You have two options:

You can use the sizes mentioned here to model a simple rectangular object to depict a solar panel. Integrate or place these panels on 3D models of your architectural designs.

OR

Sketch the design option. You can sketch the design for the whole building or detail a building element where you would like to integrate solar panels.

You can modify the panel, its orientation, size, proportion and color according to your own building design. You can apply these panels in combinations how you deem fit.

Note: Remember that BIPV can act as conventional building elements as discussed before

Calculate total energy generation for your project to convince your client.

Post-workshop Questions

Discussion